

Survey for Overcoming Pluralistic Ignorance

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Start of Block: Consent Form

Intro_T1 Welcome! Thank you for your interest in participating in our study! This survey is part of a larger research project conducted by students and faculty at Oberlin College. We are interested in getting feedback on one component of a display that will appear on public display screens in many communities. This study will take no more than 15 minutes. You will be compensated for your participation. In this study, you will be asked to answer questions about your beliefs and concerns. You may or may not see a series of slides that show pictures and quotes. You may or may not be asked to answer additional questions regarding components of the displays. You must be 18 years or older to participate in this study. There are no known risks associated with your participation in this research study. The answers and information you provide in this study will remain confidential. Should the data be published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason, and you are free to discontinue participation completely at any point for any reason and still receive payment. We recommend that you print a copy of this consent form for your records. If you have any additional questions about the study, please contact Dr. Cindy Frantz, at Cindy.Frantz@oberlin.edu or 440-775-8499. For questions concerning the rights of human subjects, please contact Dr. Michael Parkin, Chair of Oberlin College's Institutional Review Board, at ocirb@oberlin.edu or 440-775-8410.

consent I affirm that I am 18 years or older, and that I consent to participate in this research.

- Yes, I consent (1)
- No, I do not consent (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If I affirm that I am 18 years or older, and that I consent to participate in this research. = No, I do not consent

Page Break

Prolific ID What is your Prolific ID? Please note that this response should auto-fill with the correct ID

End of Block: Consent Form

Start of Block: No Exposure

Start of Block: Pro-Social CV Exposure

gencvtext This video displays a series of 12 slides featuring content produced from interviews with real people in Northeast Ohio (Cuyahoga, Medina, Lake, Geauga, and Lorain counties). Each slide features a quote, image, and attribution. Each slide will be displayed for 15 seconds, and the video will last 3 minutes. You will be asked a series of questions in response to the video. You will not be able to continue to the questions until you have watched the video. Please click the link here to watch the video: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1XvE0PzHWQ_CVeKu-bbpWC6uRrOhoBOPL/view?usp=sharing

genCVtimer Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

genslidecheck Which of the following was depicted in the slideshow you just watched?

- a goose (0)
- children (1)
- a doctor (0)
- a windmill (0)

End of Block: Pro-Social CV Exposure

Start of Block: CA CV Exposure

CACVtext This video displays a series of 12 slides featuring content produced from interviews with real people in Northeast Ohio (Cuyahoga, Medina, Lake, Geauga, and Lorain counties) that focus on climate action. Each slide features a quote, image, and attribution. Each slide will be displayed for 15 seconds, and the video will last 3 minutes. You will be asked a series of questions in response to the video. You will not be able to continue to the questions until you have watched the video. Please click the link here to watch the video: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Hbu_6kGc-JO5qumFrMDiJRSBNxlyMRRr/view?usp=sharing

CACVtimer Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

caslidecheck Which of the following was depicted in the slideshow you just watched?

- a doctor (0)
- a police officer (1)
- a goose (0)
- a windmill (0)

End of Block: CA CV Exposure

Start of Block: Norms

Norms Using the scale below, please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Agree (5)
I am aware of what others think about climate change (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People in my community are at least somewhat worried about climate change (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People in my community are taking action to to address climate change (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think it is important to address climate change (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People have a responsibility to protect the environment for future generations (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People in my community are not as concerned by climate change as me (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

People in my community do not support the government taking action to address climate change (11)

End of Block: Norms

Start of Block: PsycDistance

PsycDist Using the scale below, please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
Serious effects of climate change will mostly occur in communities far away from here (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Serious effects of climate change will occur in my local community (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't see myself as someone who will experience the effects of climate change (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My family and I will experience the effects of climate change (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: PsycDistance

Start of Block: ECAS

ECAS Using the scale below, please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
It is easy to imagine a world where we no longer use fossil fuels (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can imagine a world where politicians take effective action to address climate change (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can think of numerous methods of achieving a world where carbon emissions are reduced below current levels (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When I imagine what an ecologically sustainable existence for humans would be like, I can picture it in detail (15)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: ECAS

Start of Block: Emotions

CCemotions How strongly do you feel each of the following emotions when you think about the issue of climate change?

	Not at all (1)	Slightly (2)	Moderately (3)	Strongly (4)
Guilty (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Angry (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Betrayed (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Hopeful (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Brave (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resilient (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sad (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Afraid (14)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Optimistic (17)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Emotions

Start of Block: Human Efficacy

MitAdaptDefs In this study, we are assessing how people think and feel about climate change and responses to climate change. The survey will ask you to consider two different kinds of ways that people cope with climate change. **Mitigation** is when people work to reduce the *causes* of climate change. This means reducing greenhouse gas emissions and/or removing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. **Adaptation** involves anticipating the *impacts* of a changing climate and taking action to prevent or minimize the damage caused. For example, this might mean installing air-conditioning to deal with extreme heat, or installing sea walls to prevent flooding. Our research focuses mostly on adaptation, but you will be asked to consider both types of coping strategies in this survey.

HumanMitEff Think about humans' ability to **mitigate** (or reduce) climate change. Which of the following statements comes closest to your view?

- My community can't reduce climate change (1)
 - My community could reduce climate change, but people aren't willing to change their behavior, so we're not going to (2)
 - My community could reduce climate change, but it's unclear at this point whether we will do what's needed (3)
 - My community can reduce climate change, and we are going to do so successfully (4)
-

HumanAdaptEff Now think about whether humans can **adapt to** climate change. Can we take actions that make the impacts of climate change less disruptive? Which of the following statements comes closest to your view?

- My community can't adapt to climate change (1)
- My community could adapt to climate change, but people aren't willing to change their behavior, so we're not going to (2)
- My community could adapt to climate change, but it's unclear at this point whether we will do what's needed (3)
- My community can adapt to climate change, and we are going to do so successfully (4)

attcheck2 Please select "strongly agree" to show that you are paying attention to this question.

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Disagree (3)
- Strongly Disagree (4)

End of Block: Human Efficacy

Start of Block: Policy Support

PolicySupport Using the scale below, please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements

	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)
I support using significant tax dollars to mitigate climate emissions (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
I support using significant tax dollars to help adapt to climate change (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
I support using significant tax dollars to invest in infrastructure that supports the use of public transit (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
I support using significant tax dollars to fund the production of renewable energy (5)	<input type="radio"/>				

End of Block: Policy Support

Start of Block: Demographics

age Your age (in years)

gender What is your gender?

- Male (5)
 - Female (6)
 - Self-describe: (9) _____
-

edulevel Select the level of education you have obtained:

- Less than HS (1)
 - HS Graduate or equivalent (2)
 - Technical school (3)
 - Some college (4)
 - 2-Yr College / Associate's degree (5)
 - 4-yr College / Bachelor's degree (6)
 - Master's degree (7)
 - Doctorate (8)
-

income What is your household income, before taxes?

- Less than \$34,999 (1)
 - \$35,000 - \$74,999 (2)
 - \$75,000 - \$149,999 (3)
 - Greater than \$150,000 (4)
-

ethnicity With what ethnicity do you primarily identify?

- White (1)
- Black or African American (2)
- Asian (3)
- American Indian or Alaskan Native (4)
- Hispanic or Latino (5)
- Middle Eastern/North African (6)
- Native Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander (7)
- Other (please specify) (8)

zip Please enter your zip code:

children How many children do you have under the age of 18?

polyscale Use the scale below to indicate the extent to which you view yourself as politically liberal or conservative.

- Liberal (1)
 - __ (2)
 - __ (3)
 - Netiher (4)
 - __ (5)
 - __ (6)
 - Conservative (7)
-

regionidentity How would you describe the place you live?

- Urban (1)
 - Suburban (2)
 - Rural (3)
-

6americas How do you feel about climate change?

- Alarmed (1)
- Concerned (2)
- Cautious (3)
- Disengaged (4)
- Doubtful (5)
- Dismissive (6)

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Thank You

Q18 Thank you for your participation! Please click [here](#) or copy and paste the code below in Prolific to receive payment. C1H7BN4X The purpose of this study was to test the effectiveness of exposure to pro-environmental messages focused on climate action. Some of you were not exposed to any slides. Some of you were exposed to slide shows focused on climate action. The rest were exposed to slide shows that had no content focus.

End of Block: Thank You
